

Self-confidence and negative mood states in relation to perceived well-being among emerging adults [18 to 24 years]

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Abstract

Multiple expectations and meeting various challenges on a day-to-day basis, emerging adults are found to report varied psychological and mental health issues including depression, anxiety, panic attacks, low self-confidence and poor well-being. More specifically post pandemic when most of the youth were under lockdown finding it difficult to bounce back to the new normal. Considering this, the present study has been planned to establish the relationship among various aspects of self-confidence (i.e. general self-confidence, physical appearance self-confidence, academic self-confidence and public-speaking self confidence), negative mood affect (anxiety, stress and depression) and perceived well-being (psychological and physical) among emerging adults by using correlational research design. To accomplish the objectives, standardized tools pertaining to the same have been administered on a sample of 200 participants based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data collection is going on and will be subjected to appropriate statistical analysis including descriptive statistics followed by correlation and linear regression analysis. Final statistical outcomes will be interpreted in the light of Indian socio-cultural context.